

Using Natural Language Processing to Detect Fake News

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Abstract. Over the last few years, the world has seen what feels like an explosion of fake news due to social media and technological advancements. Even though fake news is not a new phenomenon, it is one of the biggest challenges in our digitally connected world as it spreads like wildfire impacting a significant number of individuals daily. Social media platforms such as WhatsApp, Twitter, and Facebook allow for the distribution of fake news which can potentially impact the social, political, and economic aspects of the world as it becomes more prevalent presenting dire consequences. This research benchmarks multiple Natural Language Processing (NLP) classifiers against a common dataset to determine to what extent the classifiers can detect fake news. The research also introduces natural language features that can be used to better classify fake news. The dataset includes 12 836 short statements labelled for truthfulness, subject, context/venue, speaker, state, party and prior history. The sources used to collect the dataset include political debate, TV adverts, Facebook, Twitter, interviews, news release et cetera. The results show that the accuracy of a piece of an article being classified as fake news is based on the analysis of previously seen truthful and fake news. On this basis, an increase in more samples may help improve the results and should be considered when building a fake news classifier. The results also showed an improvement in classifying fake news when bespoke features are added to the classification of articles.

Keywords: Natural Language Processing, Fake News, Detection.

1 Introduction

The growing influence of the fake news phenomenon on social media is not exactly new, but the abundance of fake news has made it harder for an individual to discern the truth as every source of information needs to be fact-checked (Thorne & Vlachos, 2018). The Internet has empowered the spread of fake news by providing multiple low-cost dissemination channels (Pollicino, 2017). The posting of fake news on discussion forums, online journals, and social media platforms requires very little specialized skill, reaching immense crowds through the span of a couple of hours. Research on the reasons for the exponential growth of fake news on social platforms has focused on psychological measures (Roozenbeek et al., 2019) and fewer efforts on how it can be avoided or prevented. The change in the history of fake news is that previously only certain individuals could effectively spread fake news, nowadays anyone with Internet

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access can easily publish it (Tsfati et al., 2020). The scale of fake news in recent history has created an issue of being able to quickly classify and filter out fake news before it is consumed. The classification of fake news using short text is important to quickly filter out or flag potential fake news before it is consumed.

In order to improve current classification techniques, it would help to extract context from the articles to try to learn how fake news mostly exaggerates or misleads with highly inconsistent information. Fake news can be classified by leveraging a large array of language models that have been built. However, building such an algorithm poses challenges such as the ability to source both truthful and fake news examples, and being able to indicate if it is clearly genuine or fabricated news (Zhou et al., 2019). According to Conroy (2015) NLP accomplishes impressive precision on existing instances of manipulated news, this is achieved by checking if the news article conforms to standard norms and styles used by expert writers. The model can detect fake news when the content is completely different from the headline or when the article incorporates words viewed as being biased or provocative. However, by preserving the original subject matter and relating content closer to the headline without using bias or provocative words, the article can easily bypass detection. Despite the outcome that is generated by the model, online platforms still rely on manual work to segregate fake news from real news.

Based on the above one may argue that some form of fact-based knowledge must be adopted alongside NLP models in order to reduce the high rate of false positives, hence making this an area of research that requires further investigation (Zhou, Guan, Bhat, & Hsu, 2019). This research proposed a technological solution to an issue that was not necessarily constructed yet unquestionably intensified by digital platforms. NLP tools were used to build a fake news detection classifier. The methodology focuses on presenting a comparative performance analysis of existing methods and incorporating different features from existing works and investigating the performance of some successful text classification techniques. The LIAR dataset was used to address these issues. The LIAR dataset includes 12 836 short statements labelled for truthfulness, subject, context/venue, speaker, state, party, and prior history. The sources used to collect the dataset include political debate, TV adverts, Facebook, Twitter, interviews, news releases etc. A lengthy analysis report is provided by the labeller to ground each judgement, and the links to all the supporting documents are also provided (Wang, 2017). The LIAR dataset is used in this research particularly for a second challenge addressed by this research, which is the classification of short text for fake news. This research will address the notion that most social media posts on platforms like Twitter allow only for short tweets of 280 characters (Perez, 2018), and thus having a solution that is able to deal with these types of fake news important.

This research benchmarked multiple NLP classifiers against a common dataset to determine to what extent the classifiers can detect fake news. Although this is a field that has been explored, examining multiple NLP classifiers on a common dataset helps ensure that there is uniformity in the research and benchmarks the models on an even fit. For this reason, the main research question of this research is: *To what extent can an NLP classifier be used to detect fake news?*

The following section provides a brief background on fake news detection mechanisms and introduces different machine learning approaches, evaluation methods and models. Section three details the methodology followed in conducting the experiment. Section four and five presents the results of the evaluation and conclusions of the study.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Fake News Detection

Research that focused on detecting deceptive review opinions in sentiment analysis was conducted by (Fayazi et al., 2015). The study utilized a crowdsourcing approach that relies heavily on the wisdom of the crowd to vote if something is false or true where the majority vote is taken as the final answer. This method uses a swarm intelligence approach however has the drawback of a delayed classification, as you need people to slowly flag the fake news and by the time the detection is done it may be too late and people have acted on the misleading information. A key part of the research that can be reused is in how the training data set for a fake news detection model needs to use a swarm approach to better filter the noise and bias from the person labelling the training dataset. The use of ensemble methods in machine learning can be used to mimic this voting by crowds however this will be more effective as it does not require a waiting period for people to vote.

The headlines of a fake news article may intend to invoke emotion or physical response from the reader by having exaggerated text, while the text or content of the text is not aligned with the headline. A hybrid deep model for fake news detection which makes use of multiple kinds of features such as allocating a score to suspicious users was later proposed by (Ruchansky, 2017). The research by Ruchansky (2017) highlights the importance of building a historical view of authors and the articles they have written in order to build confidence and understanding of the type of articles they produce.

Technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Natural Language Processing (NLP) tools offer great promise for researchers to build systems that could automatically detect fake news (Bondielli et al., 2019). Various machine learning approaches and algorithms as well as their key traits are introduced in the following sections.

2.2 Machine Learning Approaches

Machine learning is a subfield of AI that enables machines to improve at a given task with experience (Edgar & Manz, 2017). Early machine learning algorithms aimed to learn representations of basic functions. Consequently, the objective of learning was to yield a hypothesis that performed the correct classification of the training data, and early learning algorithms were intended to find such a precise fit to the data (Wittek, 2014). Modelling text brings forth many challenges as the text is known to be unstructured. Machine learning algorithms cannot work with the raw text directly; it requires well-defined fixed-length inputs and outputs and therefore the conversion of text into

vectors is imperative in order to reflect numerous linguistic properties of the text. A number of machine learning approaches exist and is briefly explained below.

Bag of words. Bag of words is a method used to represent text data when modelling, it is recognized for its great success in problems that involve language modelling and document classification (Tani et al., 2015).

Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF). TF-IDF measures how frequently a word is used in a text. The advantage with TF-IDF is that it devalues stop words. The disadvantage is if the words are not normalized there is a likelihood that the scoring would be inaccurate (Yang et al., 2008).

Word2Vec. Word2vec creates vectors that are distributed numerically as representations of word features, such as the context of individual words. It does so without human intervention (Ayyadevara, 2019). The Word2Vec algorithm finds much more efficient representations by finding vectors that represent the words. These vectors also contain semantic information about the words. It groups similar words together in the vector-space by distinguishing similarities mathematically (Kang et al., 2019).

Global vector for Word Representation (GloVe). GloVe works by firstly creating a large word-context-co-occurrence matrix, consisting of (word, context) pairs in that each of the elements contained in the matrix represents how regular a word occurs with the context. The number of contexts needs to be large as it is essentially combinatorial in size. Subsequently, they factorize the matrix to yield a lower-dimensional matrix of words and features, where each line yields a vector representation for each word. It is accomplished by minimizing the reconstruction loss which searches for lower-dimensional representations that can clarify the difference in the high-dimensional data (Pennington et al., 2014). GloVe aims to take global information into account while learning dimensions of meaning. From this initial goal, GloVe builds up a principled method of training word vectors.

2.3 Evaluation Metrics

A number of machine learning evaluation metrics exist. Due to space constraint these metrics will only be briefly explained.

Area Under the Curve (AUC). Area under the curve (AUC) is used for binary classification problems and indicates how well the probabilities from the positive classes are separated from the negative classes. AUC is the area under the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve which constitutes of true positive rate, true negative rate and false positive rate classes (Huang et al., 2005).

Recall. Recall looks at the accuracy of the model by referring to the percentage of total relevant results correctly classified by the algorithm. How recall works is that it takes the number of true positives, divides it by the number of true positives plus the number of false negatives (Carterette, 2009).

Precision. Precision is a valid choice of evaluation metric when the aim is to predict accurately. Precision is defined as the number of true positives divided by the number of true positives plus the number of false positives (Goutte et al., 2005).

F1 Score. F1 Score is the Harmonic Mean between precision and recall for a classification problem. The range for F1 Score is $[0, 1]$ which gives an indication of how precise the classifier is; in other words, how many instances it classifies correctly, as well as how robust it is; that it does not miss a significant number of instances (Goutte et al. 2005).

Accuracy. The accuracy of a model is the ratio of correct predictions to the total number of input samples. It is suited for binary as well as a multiclass classification problem. Accuracy is a valid choice of evaluation for classification problems that are well balanced and not skewed (Hossin et al., 2015). Accuracy is a measure used to determine which model is best at identifying relationships and patterns between variables in a database based on the input data.

Matthew Correlation Coefficient (MCC). Essentially MCC is a correlation coefficient between the observed and predicted binary classifications which returns a value between -1 and + 1, where -1 indicates a disagreement between prediction and observation, 0 represents a random prediction while +1 is a perfect prediction. The coefficient accounts for true and false positives and negatives and can be used even where classes are of very different sizes (Zhu, 2020).

Cohen Kappa. Cohen Kappa was initially created to test inter-rater reliability, in the most recent decades, Cohen's kappa entered the machine learning space in order to compare classifiers' performances. Despite its ubiquity, in the learning setting, there are various issues causing the kappa measure to deliver questionable outcomes, for example, its high affectability to the dispersion of the minimal aggregates. Cohen's kappa statistic is a very good measure that can handle very well both multi-class and imbalanced class problems.

Cross Validation. Cross validation is a technique used to estimate the accuracy of machine learning models whereby the model is trained using a subset of the dataset and then evaluated using the complementary subset of the dataset. In building any machine learning model it is required that the problem be properly identified so that the most suitable algorithm is chosen so that it results in the best score (Hjorth, 2017). Both non-

exhaustive methods such as Holdout (Yadav et al., 2016) and K-fold cross validation (Meijer, 2013) exist, as well as exhaustive methods such as Leave-P-Out cross validation (Hibbert, 2017).

2.4 Machine Learning Models

The following machine learning models are available:

Logistic regression. This function was developed by statisticians to explain the properties of population growth in ecology as it was rising quickly and maxing out the carrying capacity of the environment (Menard, 2010).

Support Vector Machines (SVM). SVM is a supervised machine learning algorithm that can be applied for both classification and regression use-cases. SVM works by trying to find a hyperplane that best divides a dataset into two classes by vectorising each data point with several dimensions which equates to the number of the attributes that the model considers when classifying data. SVM aims to maximize predictive accuracy while avoiding overfitting to the data.

Tree Based Models. Tree based models are non-parametric supervised learning methods used for classification and regression. The objective is to create a model that predicts the estimation of an objective variable by taking in basic choice guidelines derived from the data features. Examples of tree-based models include Random forest (Xue et al, 2015), Gradient boosting algorithm (Wang et al, 2018), XGBoost (Chen et al, 2016) and Lightweight GBM (Machado et al, 2019).

3 Methodology

Multiple types of machine learning models were trained on the LIAR dataset using only the text field in the data. The models that performed the best on the dataset were selected based on their ability to properly classify fake or real news statements. The LIAR dataset has become the de-facto standard in modern fake news detection benchmarks and is publicly available. The dataset contains 12.8K manually labelled short statements in various contexts from Politifact¹, which provides detailed analysis reports and links to source documents for each case (Wang, 2017). After the dataset was collected various pre-processing methods were employed and some machine learning models were trained and evaluated on the data. The best performing models were measured on specific metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score. Further comparison between traditional NLP methods and deep learning context-based models was evaluated. The research were finalized by synthesizing and interpreting the results.

¹ <https://www.politifact.com>

4 Modelling Experiments and Results

This section briefly details (due to space constraint) the most important model training process and results and a summary of the evaluation results.

4.1 Model Training and Results

The initial round of models was used to build multiple base pipelines that worked to extract the statement field in the data and run it with TFDIF, GloVe, or Bespoke features as the initial step of pre-processing and feature extracting. The model that performed the best was the GloVe Random Forest as it showed the highest F1 Score, at 38%. A major problem that was observed with most of the models in the first modelling approach is that the scoring difference between the training and testing was so vastly different. It was clear that the highly complex models are overfitting the dataset and that good generalized models need to be found. This then informed the approach for the second round of modelling which focused more on a cross validation type of training which ensured that the model generalizes across multiple samples of the data.

Given the results from the initial model, GloVe emerged as a text feature extraction mechanism was a good way of getting meaning from the data. All the models were then trained on a combination of GloVe and Bespoke features that were created for this project. Given the large dimensions of the GloVe vector for each document which was 96 elements in size, dimensionality reduction using UMAP (Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection for Dimension Reduction) was also employed (McInnes et al., 2018). This resulted in a training set that had 49 features which comprised of 39 bespoke features and 10 components from the redacted GloVe features using UMAP. Part of the pre-processing of the data is the creation of new features based on interactions between features and polynomial features that create combinations of features. This expands the data set to 341 features, for the sake of simplicity where it will only cover these features if they appear in the top 15 features list.

5-Fold cross validation was employed and included the LIAR datasets validation set in the overall dataset. The 5-Fold cross validation will be based on 80% of data with a 20% unseen dataset for us to use for evaluation purposes. After preparing all this data for training, the dataset was ran across multiple models.

When using the dataset in the second approach, it was seen that the tree-based ensemble methods are the best models at classifying the dataset. The results from the mean 5-fold cross validation scores showed more stable results. The best model being Gradient Boosting Machine with an AUC of 61% which is 11% higher than a random model.

From the top models, hyperparameter tuning using a grid search was used to tune the models.

After tuning the models, the top model was benchmarked. This was done by training on instances of the model on each fold and testing out the results. The performance of the top model was tested on the unseen data.

Table 1. Validation Results

Model	Accu- racy	AUC	Recall	Prec.	F1	Kappa	MCC
Gradient Boosting Classifier	0.6451	0.6012	0.1015	0.503	0.1689	0.0563	0.0857
Bagging Classifier	0.6751	0.7404	0.1259	0.7574	0.2159	0.1275	0.2105

The model performed very much consistent with how it performed on the training set. This makes it a very stable method as the training cross validation score matches the unseen validation data.

Using a bagging model significantly improves the performance of the model as the model's results jumped to 74% AUC with an improved MCC as well as F1 Score. The results of both these models are illustrated in Table 1.

4.2 Summarizing Evaluation Results

From the models in the first stage, it was observed that the first benchmarks look like and the results that can be achieved with TFIDF vs GloVe vs GloVe UMAP. Using TFIDF, it was shown that simplistic models can extract more meaning from the data where more complex models and mainly the three based models seem to over-fit especially when using the default settings and underperform on the dataset. Given that there is little text in the statements made in the LIAR dataset it would make sense that the model should not be highly complex as this may generate very highly biased models that would not give the best results. Model performance was also evaluated when the GloVe embeddings are used on the data. In the second approach, a more streamlined approach was followed by using the same pre-processing technique which showed great success in the first round which was the GloVe+UMAP+Bespoke feature approach. The Bespoke method tied in the use of text generated, entity-based features, and sentiment-based features. In this approach, a wider range of models were considered and their performance were evaluated from mean 4-fold cross validation. The best model was selected by using the AUC as a metric. To see if that model could be improved further, the bagging approach was employed by using 10 versions of the top model and training them as voting classifiers. This improved the results significantly to 74% AUC. The resulting model was able to classify short text in the LIAR dataset as Fake or Real. The shortcomings of this model are:

- **Text Length:** The LIAR dataset is based on very short texts and this task would be even hard for a human to do without context.
- **Using just Text:** Most attempts at training a classifier on the LIAR dataset do this by using all fields in the dataset. The proposed model will classify fake news solely based on text.
- **Data Gap:** Although the dataset is extensive it would be helpful if the dataset was much larger

5 Research Findings and Conclusion

From the previous section, it emerged that the GBM model was the best model. The model's parameters are as follows:

```
GradientBoostingClassifier (ccp_alpha=0.0, criterion='friedman_mse', init=None,
learning_rate=0.1, loss='deviance', max_depth=3,
max_features=None, max_leaf_nodes=None,
min_impurity_decrease=0.0, min_impurity_split=None,
min_samples_leaf=1, min_samples_split=2,
min_weight_fraction_leaf=0.0, n_estimators=100,
n_iter_no_change=None, presort='deprecated',
random_state=6387, subsample=1.0, tol=0.0001,
validation_fraction=0.1, verbose=0,
warm_start=False)
```

The model has a maximum depth of 3 which shows that the model creates a very simplistic relationship within the data. This is the main metric that emerged when considering the parameters. It supported the notion that given the short text found in the LIAR dataset it would make sense that the models that do draw inference from this data are too complex. The maximum depths ensure that the relationships are not too complex. From the results of the model, it showed that the GBM model has a cross validation AUC mean of 60% and this can be seen from the ROC Curve shown in Fig 1.

Fig. 1. ROC for Gradient boosting classifier

The model performance was evaluated across other metrics which show that the model has a hard time classifying documents as fake or real. This is to be expected as most of the text looks the same in the statements of the LIAR dataset. The model seems more conservative in predicting fake news and this is given that fake news is the minor class in the fake news or fake statement problem.

The precision-recall curve was explored to determine the trade-off between precision and recall for different thresholds. The models show a high precision which gives the view that the model has a relatively low false-positive rate which helps ensure that the model is precise about its prediction of a fake statement.

Fig. 2. GBM classification matrix

The chart below shows the average precision to be around 44%.

Fig. 3. Precision-Recall Curve for Gradient Boosting Classifier

In response to the research question, the literature presented in section 2 indicates that NLP is being used as a means to detect fake news. This research, proposed steps to extract information from text and use machine learning to classify text into fake or real news. Section 4 briefly detailed the results of the experiment to evaluate the best model to achieve this.

This research highlighted that the best way to discern if a model is doing well or not is by comparing the different types of metrics. Cross validating was added to ensure that the models' output was not being affected by sample bias and that the key results derived from the model were a genuine performance.

Pipeline and pre-processing steps were proposed to train the models. The final model structure showed the most promising results, which was to use GloVe word embedding with bespoke features. This incorporated the notion that to classify if an article is fake or not you have to understand how something was said using the bespoke text features by getting a numerical GloVe embedding of the text. A major drawback was the length of text found in the LIAR dataset. The text is rather short and does not give the model too much to work with, however, this is also an advantage of the model as learning from short text mimics a lot about today's society in the world of social media where fake news can be shared by a single tweet. Although complex, this research serves as a first view of what is possible with using just short text to classify fake news.

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